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Capstone Project

**UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
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**OVERTIME MANAGEMENT SYSTEM
FOR UNIX MANILA TEAM OF TELUS INTERNATIONAL DIGITAL SOLUTIONS**

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**OVERTIME MANAGEMENT SYSTEM
FOR UNIX MANILA TEAM OF TELUS INTERNATIONAL DIGITAL SOLUTIONS**

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ABSTRACT

The Unix Manila team is a part of Telus International Philippines, Inc.'s Digital Solutions group and consists of 33 systems administrators who provide 24/7 technical support for maintaining the UNIX servers of Telus Communications Canada. To ensure high-quality service to customers, the team occasionally works overtime, which includes covering for absent team members, a practice known as "fill-in." The team previously used a makeshift tool built in Microsoft Sharepoint to manage fill-in requests and track leave projections, however, due to Telus's recent partnership with Google, most applications were migrated to the Google platform and in September 2022, Microsoft Sharepoint was decommissioned. To replace this, the team developed the Overtime Management System (OMS), a web-based system built in PHP, CSS, HTML, JavaScript, Bootstrap, and MariaDB. In addition to the fill-in application and leave tracking, OMS also includes new features such as offset tracking, additional resource management, and report generation. The system is designed to be scalable, reusable, and flexible, allowing for easy migration in the event of future changes to the organization's infrastructure.

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Chapter I

INTRODUCTION

The Unix Manila team is under the Digital Solutions business unit of Telus International Philippines, Inc. (TIP). It is composed of 33 systems administrators (SA) who provide 24/7 technical support to maintain the UNIX servers of Telus Communications Canada. The team works in a rotating shift schedule that changes every two (2) weeks and is divided into three (3) shifts – morning, mid and night.

When a team member is absent, it is expected that he or she must be covered by another team member from a different shift. This practice is known as “fill-in”. A team member may also be asked to work outside his or her shift depending on the workload and demand. The team calls this “additional resource” or “add resource” for short. Both “fill-in” and “add resource” are being paid monetarily based on the overtime premium rate.

There are some occasions that a team member attends non-billable activities such as meetings and corporate events. These are being compensated with offset days. Offset days may also be used to accommodate personal matters or special circumstances involving the team members. Therefore, offset arrangements are only internal between the team member and the manager. There is no system that records these activities. When a team member uses his or her offset day, he or she is considered present for the day, hence, he or she cannot be filled in.

The abovementioned overtime activities are common practices in the team. An application organizing these activities would help the team manage the resources available in every shift. It shall also help the manager review all application requests

and have his or her own system in making a decision on who to approve. This is because there are many factors being considered by the manager as an approver. Getting approved is not usually on a first come first serve basis. For instance, if the team member who is on leave is a junior systems administrator, then the one who will most likely get approved to fill-in is also a junior. The approval may also depend on the current financial standing of the team for the month.

Chapter II

REVIEW OF EXISTING ALTERNATIVES

The team had an old tool for managing fill-in requests and tracking leave projections. It was a simple makeshift tool built in Microsoft Sharepoint. This tool has a calendar displaying which date/s a team member is on leave, and has a table listing down who was approved to fill-in.

Unfortunately, because of the recent partnership of Telus with Google, most work applications of the organization were migrated to the Google platform. Among the work applications affected by this move is Microsoft Sharepoint. In September 2022, Microsoft Sharepoint was decommissioned. Temporarily, the team is using Google Form and Google Sheet for fill-in applications and leave tracking.

However, the problem with Google Form and Google Sheets is that they are not customizable and do not give users flexibility around the system. For example, submitted entries can no longer be deleted by the user. If a wrong entry was made and really needs to be deleted, the user must contact the creator or administrator to get this removed from the backend. Furthermore, in order to modify an entry, the user would have to find the receipt sent by Google Form to his or her email, edit his or her response, then re-submit again. There are also security concerns as there are limitations on setting a certain level of access or visibility to a specific user.

Chapter III

PROJECT DETAILS

3.1 Overview

To address the stated problem in the previous section, a new system called Overtime Management System (OMS) was developed. This is a web-based system allowing team members to apply not only for fill-in, but also for other types of overtime such as offset and additional resources. This system shall also generate reports summarizing the team's overtime activities to provide insights of any financial impact in the management perspective.

3.2 Theoretical Framework

Figure 1 - The 3-tier Architecture Model

The development of the OMS is based on the 3-tier architecture model ^[4]. In this model, the Presentation Tier (front-end), Application tier (back-end), and the

Data tier (database) are autonomous from each other. This allowed the proponent to independently update specific components of the code without affecting the system as a whole.

3.3 Technologies Used

Front End	HTML, CSS, Javascript, Bootstrap 4
Web Server	Apache 2.4.41
Programming Language	PHP 7.4.3
IDE	Brackets 1.14
Database Server	MariaDB 10.2.38
Database Administration	PhpMyAdmin

3.4 System Design

3.4.1 System Features

User profiles

- Like any system, OMS has an Administrator user that has absolute access to all the functionalities of the system. This privilege is given to users who are the decision-makers of the team or in managerial positions.
- The manager can add, view, remove and update team member's profiles.
- All users can change their own password.

Paid Time Offs (PTOs) and Offsets

- The team member can plot his or her projected leave/s or offset/s in a calendar so that the team could plan and manage their resource on a specific date ahead of time.

- The team member can indicate the type of leave (i.e. PTO, Holiday Leave, Birthday Leave, Bereavement Leave, etc.) he or she is plotting.
- The team member can modify his or her own plotted leave/s or offset/s.
- All users can view the plotted leaves of the team to determine who to fill-in to.
- The manager can view the offset balance and offset history of the team.
- The team member can view his or her own offset balance and offset history.

Overtime Requests

- Overtime is categorized into three (3) categories: fill-in, offset, or additional resource.
- The team member is able to submit a request to fill-in for a team member who is on leave. Offset days cannot be filled-in by a team member.
- The team member is able to submit a request to avail offset day and provide details how and when this offset was earned to justify the request.
- The team member is able to cancel their fill-in, offset and add resource requests.
- The manager can review, approve and reject requests.
- The manager is able to manage user accounts.

Overtime Summary

- All users are able to view the summary of the team's requests.
- The manager is able to view and extract the overtime hours of the team monthly and annually.
- The manager is able to view the leave usage of each team member.
- The manager is able to view the offset balance of each team member.

The figure below (Figure 2) is a Use Case diagram illustrating the features of OMS.

Figure 2 - Use Case Diagram for OMS

tables. The *request* table was created to manage all the data submissions in the system since they all have the same attributes such as the *Requester*, *Approver*, *RequestDate*, *Comments* and *LastModified*. The *years* table is not associated with all other tables as it is only used to store the years in the filtering of overtime activities. The view tables were created to simplify the long join SQL statements which were used to display a summary of overtime activities, leave usage, and quick view components found at the home page of the system.

3.5 Implementation

3.5.1 Process Model

Figure 4 - Waterfall Model

The process model that was followed in developing OMS is the Waterfall Model. In this model, the project activities were distributed into linear sequential phases. Each phase is being completed before moving on to the next phase. This is recommended for small projects such as the OMS since the likelihood of having incremental changes in the requirements is very minimal. Furthermore, this methodology is milestone-oriented which is suitable to the schedule and deliverables required in the IS295A and IS295B courses.

3.5.2 Project Schedule

TASK	START	END
Phase 1 - Planning		
1.1 Problem Definition		
1.2 Requirements Gathering	IS295A	
1.3 Documentation fo SRS and Proposal		
Phase 2 - Analysis and Design		
2.1 Designing of Database Schema	9/12/22	10/2/22
2.2 Creation of Classes, Methods and Prototypes in Backend	9/14/22	11/15/22
2.3 Building of Front End	9/19/22	11/7/22
Phase 3 - Implementation		
3.1 Coding	10/3/22	12/11/22
Phase 4 - Testing		
4.1 System Testing, and Bug Fixing	11/15/22	12/11/22
Phase 5 - Deployment and Maintenance		
5.1 Deployment	12/12/22	12/18/22
5.2 User Training and Turn-over	1/9/23	1/13/23

Figure 5 - Project Gantt Chart for OMS

The project gantt chart in Figure 5 illustrates the schedule of the tasks lined up in developing OMS. The dates indicated in the chart included holidays and weekends. An average of three hours were spent per day.

The planning phase of the project was completed during the IS295A course. The activities included interviewing the stakeholder to define the problem, gathering the requirements to aid in designing the system, and composing a project proposal for approval.

The succeeding phases were accomplished during the IS295B course where most time was used in building the system prototype.

After the turnover, the system shall be maintained by the proponent since she is part of the UNIX Manila team who will be using the system.

3.6 Resulting System

Figure 6 - OMS Homepage (Administrator User View)

Figure 6.1 - OMS Homepage (Non-Administrator User View)

The OMS Homepage contains quick views of pending requests, names of who are not present, filling-in and working as additional resources today. The shift schedule determiner can also be found in this page which allows the users to check their shift schedule at a specific date since it rotates every two weeks. The main menu is located at the left hand side of the page leading to the major functionalities of the system. The options available in this menu differ based on the type of user logged in (see Figure 6 and Figure 6.1). The administrator user has more options than the non-administrator user since it has absolute access to the system (see 3.4.1 System Features).

List of Unix Tier 3 Team Members

Search: All Active Locked Inactive

Show 10 entries

Last Name	First Name	Employee ID	Email	Role	Status	Added By	Date Added	Last Modified	Last Login	Action
Asinas	Miya	x171849	miya.asinas@telus.com	Administrator	Active	Administrator	2022-10-02	2022-12-07 05:34:44	2023-01-02 18:18:37	✎
Catacutan	Grace	x142223	grace.catacutan@telus.com	Member	Active	Administrator	2022-12-21	2022-12-21 00:13:19	2022-12-21 00:16:07	✎
Cooper	Sheldon	x111111	sheldon.cooper@telus.com	Member	Active	Administrator	2022-10-02	2022-12-21 07:59:08	2022-12-13 19:30:17	✎
Dalina	Reggie	x148402	reggie.dalina@telus.com	Administrator	Active	Administrator	2022-12-21	2022-12-21 00:12:19	2022-12-21 00:12:19	✎
Donato	Aaron	x145188	aaron.donato@telus.com	Member	Active	Administrator	2022-12-21	2022-12-21 00:14:51	2022-12-21 00:14:51	✎
Fowler	Amy Farah	x777777	amy.farah.fowler@telus.com	Member	Active	Administrator	2022-12-04	2022-12-04 16:52:15	2022-12-13 19:44:10	✎
Hofstadter	Leonard	x222222	leonard.hofstadter@telus.com	Member	Active	Administrator	2022-11-24	2022-12-21 08:00:22	2022-12-23 00:05:53	✎

Figure 7: View Team Members

Figure 7 displays all the users registered to the system and their information such as *last name*, *first name*, *employee ID*, *email*, and *role*. They can also be filtered based on their account status: *active*, *locked* and *inactive*. This page is only visible to administrator users.

Figure 8: Leave Tracker

The leaves of the team are plotted in the *Leave Tracker* page (see Figure 8). The names of the team members and the type of leave are displayed in the calendar. The calendar can be changed into *month*, *week*, *day* or *list* view.

Figure 8.1: Team's Leave Usage

The *Team's Leave Usage* page (Figure 8.1) provides the total leave days that every team member has used per month. This enables the team to budget their leave credits throughout the year.

Team's Fill-in Requests

Fill-in Date: All My Requests

Show entries

Fill-in Date	Applicant's Name	SA On Leave	Shift	Duration	Date Submitted	Application Status	Date Approved	Action
01/03/2022	Wolowitz, Howard	Hofstadter, Penny	Mid	Full Shift	12/13/2022 19:28:33	Approved	12/13/2022 19:31:59	
01/12/2023	Wolowitz, Howard	Hofstadter, Leonard	Mid	Full Shift	01/12/2023 07:27:41	Pending		
01/14/2022	Wolowitz, Howard	Koothrappali, Rajesh	Night	Full Shift	12/13/2022 19:28:55	Approved	12/13/2022 19:32:09	
01/31/2022	Cooper, Sheldon	Fowler, Amy Farah	Morning	Full Shift	12/13/2022 19:30:52	Approved	12/13/2022 19:32:16	
02/02/2022	Wolowitz, Howard	Fowler, Amy Farah	Morning	Full Shift	12/13/2022 19:29:25	Approved	12/13/2022 19:32:21	
03/01/2022	Cooper, Sheldon	Asinas, Miya	Mid	Full Shift	12/13/2022 19:30:33	Approved	12/13/2022 19:32:28	
03/03/2022	Wolowitz, Howard	Rostenkowski, Bernadette	Mid	Full Shift	12/13/2022 19:30:03	Approved	12/13/2022 19:32:34	
03/10/2022	Wolowitz, Howard	Cooper, Sheldon	Night	Full Shift	12/13/2022 19:29:47	Approved	12/13/2022 19:32:41	
04/05/2022	Cooper, Sheldon	Hofstadter, Penny	Mid	Full Shift	12/13/2022 19:31:17	Approved	12/13/2022 19:32:48	
04/06/2022	Rostenkowski, Bernadette	Hofstadter, Penny	Mid	Full Shift	12/13/2022 19:37:14	Approved	12/13/2022 19:42:49	

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Figure 9: Fill-in Requests

Figure 9 shows a list of fill-in requests submitted by the team in a table form. This page is available to both administrator and non-administrator user accounts. In this way, all team members have visibility on all submitted fill-in applications and their status. As a non-admin user, the team member can only edit his or her own request, hence, the eye icon is disabled on the rows of requests that are not his or hers.

Team's Add Resource Requests

Date: MM/DD/YYYY All Approved Pending Rejected Cancelled Search

Show 10 entries

Start Time	End Time	Duration	Applicant Name	Date Submitted	Application Status	Date Approved	Action
01/24/2022 10:00:00	01/24/2022 14:00:00	4 hour(s)	Rostenkowski, Bernadette	12/13/2022 19:34:35	Approved	12/13/2022 19:42:21	🔗
02/15/2022 00:00:00	02/15/2022 04:00:00	4 hour(s)	Fowler, Amy Farah	12/13/2022 19:45:05	Approved	12/13/2022 19:45:22	🔗
04/01/2022 10:00:00	04/01/2022 14:00:00	4 hour(s)	Hofstadter, Leonard	12/13/2022 19:38:50	Approved	12/13/2022 19:42:27	🔗
06/25/2022 00:00:00	06/25/2022 06:00:00	6 hour(s)	Fowler, Amy Farah	12/13/2022 19:44:39	Approved	12/13/2022 19:45:28	🔗
08/14/2022 11:00:00	08/14/2022 22:00:00	11 hour(s)	Rostenkowski, Bernadette	12/13/2022 19:35:21	Approved	12/13/2022 19:42:33	🔗
09/13/2022 00:00:00	09/13/2022 06:00:00	6 hour(s)	Hofstadter, Leonard	12/13/2022 19:38:31	Approved	12/13/2022 19:42:38	🔗
12/14/2022 10:00:00	12/14/2022 14:00:00	4 hour(s)	Hofstadter, Leonard	12/13/2022 06:19:43	Approved	12/13/2022 06:30:21	🔗

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Figure 10: Add Resource Requests

The applications for additional resources are being managed in the *Add Resource Requests* page (see Figure 10). The interface and process are similar to fill-in requests except that there is no SA on leave that needs to be selected in the application form.

Team's Offset Requests

Offset Date: MM/DD/YYYY All Approved Pending Rejected Cancelled Search

Show 10 entries

Start Time	End Time	Total Hours	Request Type	Applicant's Name	Date Submitted	Application Status	Date Approved	Action
01/11/2023 22:00:00	01/12/2023 02:00:00	4 hour(s)	Add	Fowler, Amy Farah	01/12/2023 08:01:08	Approved	01/12/2023 08:02:33	🔗
01/11/2023 22:00:00	01/12/2023 02:00:00	4 hour(s)	Add	Fowler, Amy Farah	01/12/2023 07:54:23	Cancelled		🔗
01/12/2023 06:00:00	01/12/2023 10:00:00	4 hour(s)	Use	Fowler, Amy Farah	01/12/2023 08:02:01	Approved	01/12/2023 08:02:41	🔗
01/19/2023 22:00:00	01/20/2023 05:00:00	7 hour(s)	Add	Fowler, Amy Farah	01/12/2023 08:53:42	Approved	01/12/2023 10:12:55	🔗
10/01/2022 19:00:00	10/02/2022 00:00:00	5 hour(s)	Add	Cooper, Sheldon	12/13/2022 06:53:27	Approved	12/13/2022 06:54:41	🔗
11/10/2022 06:00:00	11/10/2022 10:00:00	4 hour(s)	Use	Cooper, Sheldon	12/13/2022 06:54:31	Approved	12/13/2022 06:54:47	🔗
12/01/2022 00:00:00	12/01/2022 06:00:00	6 hour(s)	Add	Wolowitz, Howard	12/13/2022 18:18:05	Approved	12/13/2022 19:02:16	🔗
12/01/2022 00:00:00	12/01/2022 07:00:00	7 hour(s)	Add	Rostenkowski, Bernadette	12/13/2022 07:01:13	Approved	12/13/2022 07:01:43	🔗
12/07/2022 06:00:00	12/07/2022 10:00:00	4 hour(s)	Use	Rostenkowski, Bernadette	12/13/2022 07:08:14	Approved	12/13/2022 07:09:51	🔗

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Figure 11: Offset Requests

Like the *Fill-in Requests* (Figure 9) and *Add Resource Requests* (Figure 10) pages, the *Offset Requests* page lists down all the requests related to offset. The requests can also be filtered based on their application status. The only difference is that an offset request has two types: *add* or *use*.

The screenshot shows a form titled "Create Offset Request". At the top, there are two radio buttons: "Add Offset" (which is selected) and "Use Offset". Below these are four input fields: "Date of Offset" with a placeholder "MM/DD/YYYY", "Start Time" with a placeholder "HH:MM 24-hour format", "End Time" with a placeholder "HH:MM 24-hour format", and "Duration". Below the "Duration" field is a large text area labeled "Comment/Justification". At the bottom of the form are two buttons: "Save" and "Cancel".

Figure 11.1: Create Offset Request

A team member shall select *add* in the offset application form (see Figure 11.1) if he or she would like to record his or her earned offset hours for future use. Once approved by the manager, he or she can already avail these offset hours by submitting a new offset application and selecting *use* as request type. Again, this is subject to manager's approval. The name of the team member who has been approved to avail his or her offset shall reflect in the *Offset Tracker* calendar (similar

to the *Leave Tracker* calendar). All of these offset information are being recorded in the *Offset History* page (see Figure 11.2).

Offset History of Cooper, Sheldon

Show entries

Date	Added	Used	Balance	Comments/Justification
10/01/2022 19:00:00	5.0 hours	0.0 hours	5 hours	Attended dinner for newly promotees at Marriot
11/10/2022 06:00:00	0.0 hours	4.0 hours	1 hours	

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Figure 11.2: Offset History

UNIX TIER 3

Welcome, Administrator

Team's OT Summary (in hours)

Period: All Fill-in Add Resource [Search](#)

[Copy](#) [CSV](#) [Print](#)

Employee Name	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Total
Asinas, Miya	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	8
Catacutan, Grace	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cooper, Sheldon	8	0	8	8	0	8	0	0	0	0	0	8	40
Dalina, Reggie	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
De Leon, Aurelio	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Donato, Aaron	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Fowler, Amy Farrah	0	4	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	10
Hofstadter, Leonard	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	4	14
Hofstadter, Penny	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Josue, Cris	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

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Figure 12: Overtime Summary

The Overtime Summary page shown in Figure 12 lists the total number of hours used by each team member on a monthly and annual basis. This view is available only to the administrator users. The result can be copied and pasted to a notepad, extracted into a CSV file, and printed.

Chapter IV

PROJECT ASSESSMENT

4.1. Unit Testing

Before integrating the backend to the front end, APIs were being initially tested via Postman. Generally, the process of testing goes as follows:

1. A link associated with the API in the folder structure of the project is picked, and inputted as URL in Postman.
2. The REST API method that will eventually be used when processing the input in the backend is then selected.
3. The body of the request is constructed with the necessary parameters required by the API being tested. These parameters normally reflect the ones that will be put in the HTML form.
4. Click *Send*. Validate if the appropriate JSON Response is displayed as output and if the database has changed due to the nature of the API being tested. Associated tables should also be checked.

4.2 Regression Testing

After the front and back end were integrated with each other, the regression testing was performed. This test was being run every milestone change made on the feature or after a bug fix was committed to the code. It validates whether the new change impacted a previously working functionality or caused new bugs.

The approach to this test was to run through the feature where the change was made first, then its associated features, and finally the rest of the system. For instance, if the change made was on the *leave usage* functionality, then test scenarios under leave management would be performed next. After that, other

non-related features would be tested such as the user management, fill-in management, add resource management and so on.

4.3 System Usability Testing

4.3.1 Test Objective

The objective of the usability test is to understand how real users would interact on the system, and to identify which area/s it could be improved. The proponent acted as the test administrator. At the end of the evaluation, the test administrator was expected to determine the following:

- a. Does the system provide information effectively?
- b. What are the features that are most or least liked by the user?
- c. Are the participants able to navigate easily through the website?
- d. How likely will they choose to use the system?

4.3.2 Participants

A total of ten (10) participants had been invited in the usability testing sessions. Eight (8) of them are part of the Unix Manila Team.

4.3.3 Materials/Tools used for testing

- a. Web Browser
- b. Google Forms
- c. Google Meet

4.3.4 Procedure

4.3.4.1 Orientation

The system usability testing was conducted through a virtual meeting in Google Meet. Before commencing with the system evaluation, each participant was given an orientation of the overall testing process. The test administrator ensured that every step below had been covered before handing the system over:

- a. Provide a brief introduction of the website and discuss the testing process.
- b. Explain the environment setup and confirm that the participant is comfortable with it.
- c. Ask the participant to share his/her screen via Google Meet.
- d. Have the participant sign the Participation and Disclosure Agreement in Google Forms.
- e. Have the participant complete the Respondent's Profile in Google Forms.
- f. Ask the participant if they have any questions.
- g. Remind the participant that there is a Post-Test Questionnaire in Google Forms to be completed after completing the tasks.
- h. Ask the participant to access the system. Verify if the login page is ready.
- i. Ask the participant to begin.

4.3.4.2 Evaluation

During the test, the participant was sharing his or her screen so that the test administrator could observe and take down notes. The test administrator was also on standby in case there were any questions related to the tasks.

The participant was allowed to complete the abovementioned tasks at his or her own pace.

4.3.4.3 Debriefing

After completing the tasks, each participant was asked to complete a brief post-test questionnaire in Google Forms. It is composed of two parts.

The first part of the questionnaire is a System Usability Scale (SUS) developed by John Brooke. This methodology allowed the project owners to get a definitive result from the usability testing. There are ten (10) standard questions with five response options – from Strongly Agree (5) to Strongly Disagree (1):

1. I think that I would like to use this system frequently.
2. I found the system unnecessarily complex.
3. I thought the system was easy to use.
4. I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system.
5. I found the various functions in this system were well integrated.
6. I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system.
7. I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly.
8. I found the system very complicated to use.
9. I felt very confident using the system.
10. I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system.

In the second part, the participants were asked to share their feedback about their experience in using the system by answering the questions below:

1. What features of this system did you like the most?
2. What features of this system did you like the least?
3. Do you feel that the pictures or icons used are recognizable and facilitate ease of use and understanding?
4. Is the navigation intuitive?

4.3.5 System Usability Testing Result

The responses of the participants from the first part of the post-test questionnaire were tallied and recorded (see Appendix B). To obtain their equivalent SUS score, these values were calculated using the steps below:

1. For each of the odd numbered questions, subtract 1 from the score.
2. For each of the even numbered questions, subtract their value from 5.
3. Take the resulting values, and add up the total score. Then, multiply it by 2.5.

The raw SUS scores obtained from the above computation were averaged arriving at the value of **95**. To translate this value into a more meaningful result, it was evaluated using Jeff Sauro's "*Five Ways To Interpret a SUS Score*" [5], wherein the score has a corresponding rating per category: Percentile, Grade, Adjective, Acceptability; and Net Promoter Score (NPS). See Table 1.

SUS	Percentile	Grade	Adjective	Acceptability	NPS
84.1-100	96-100	A+	Best Imaginable	Acceptable	Promoter
80.8-84.0	90-95	A-	Excellent	Acceptable	Promoter
78.9-80.7	85-89	A-		Acceptable	Promoter
77.2-78.8	80-84	B+		Acceptable	Passive
74.1 – 77.1	70 – 79	B-		Acceptable	Passive
72.6 – 74.0	65 – 69	B-		Acceptable	Passive
71.1 – 72.5	60 – 64	C+	Good	Acceptable	Passive
65.0 – 71.0	41 – 59	C-		Marginal	Passive
62.7 – 64.9	35 – 40	C-		Marginal	Passive
51.7 – 62.6	15 – 34	D	OK	Marginal	Detractor
25.1 – 51.6	2– 14	F	Poor	Not Acceptable	Detractor
0-25	0-1.9	F	Worst Imaginable	Not Acceptable	Detractor

Table 1: Interpreting the SUS Scores

The percentile ranking in the table was based on 68 being the 50th percentile -- it is the average SUS score as per industry standards. Closely related to percentile

rankings are the letter grades, a commonly used rating scheme in schools, where A denotes superior performance, C as passing and F as a failing mark. The SUS score can also be interpreted through descriptions (Adjective) and acceptability. And lastly, the Net Promoter Score (NPS) pertains to the likelihood of the system to be recommended.

Based on the previous chart, the SUS score of 95 indicates that OMS attained the following rating:

SUS	Percentile	Grade	Adjective	Acceptability	NPS
95	96-100	A+	Best Imaginable	Acceptable	Promoter

Table 1.1: The SUS rating for OMS

Chapter V

DISCUSSIONS

There are several learnings that have been noted while developing this project.

First, the proponent learned about prioritization. While all features are important, it should be accepted that not all of them could be implemented at once. This is why in the software development industry, there are succeeding releases and versions of the system.

Next, the backend design is the building block of the system. If the back end was not carefully designed at the start, the developer may encounter more problems throughout the development. And there would be major changes in the code.

Third, the need to change some features may only be realized during the development phase. For instance, in the offset management feature, it was realized that in order to verify the offset balance per individual, there should be a history of their activities. Hence, the offset history functionality was added.

And finally, the proponent realized that there is no perfect system. There will always be flaws and room for improvements. Therefore, enhancements are inevitable.

Chapter VI

CONCLUSION

As a conclusion, OMS is a useful tool for the UNIX Manila team. It is expected that this system will efficiently manage the overtime activities of the team.

In the previous chapter, it was discussed that there should be a prioritization of features given the limited time and resources available in the course. During the development of OMS, the functionalities per feature were classified as *essential*, *expected*, *desired* and *optional*. This guided the proponent on which task to accomplish first.

The following tables list the completion status per feature at the end of the project.

Feature	Priority	Completed	Completed but buggy	Not Completed
Login	Essential	✓		
Team Member Account Administration	Essential	✓		
Change Password	Expected	✓		
Unlock User Account	Expected	✓		

Table 2: User Account Management

Feature	Priority	Completed	Completed but buggy	Not Completed
Plot projected date of leave	Essential	✓		
Plot projected date of offset	Essential	✓		

Feature	Priority	Completed	Completed but buggy	Not Completed
View Offset Balance	Expected	✓		
View Offset History	Expected	✓		
Quick view of who is not present today	Optional	✓		
Quick view of who is the additional resource today	Optional	✓		
Shift Schedule Determiner	Optional	✓		

Table 3: Leave and Offset Management

Feature	Priority	Completed	Completed but buggy	Not Completed
Submit Overtime Request	Expected	✓		
Update details of Overtime Request	Expected	✓		
Cancel Overtime Request	Expected	✓		
Approve or reject Overtime Request	Expected	✓		
View status of overtime request	Expected	✓		
Pending Requests Count	Optional			

Table 4: Requests Management

Feature	Priority	Completed	Completed but buggy	Not Completed
View Summary of Team's Overtime Hours	Desired	✓		

Feature	Priority	Completed	Completed but buggy	Not Completed
Extract Summary of Team's Overtime Hours	Desired	✓		
Print Summary of Team's Overtime Hours	Desired	✓		

Table 5: Reports Management

Those functionalities classified as *optional* above were not originally included in the proposal. These are the shift schedule determiner, the quick view of who are not present today, and the quick view of who are the additional resources today. They are nice-to-have features that turned out to be valuable additions to the system. The stakeholders appreciated them as these would help the team plan their leaves or offset days, and also assist the shift primes or team leaders in the distribution of the tasks every start of the shift. Another optional functionality that has been added is the pending requests count of fill-ins, offsets and add resources found at the home page.

Chapter VII

FUTURE WORK

The system has a big potential to be a more valuable and useful tool to UNIX Manila Team especially when new features will be added and more improvements will be made. The proponent would like to recommend the following enhancements for future upgrades and later releases.

7.1 Request Notification

Presently, the system only displays a total number of pending requests in the home page as a quick reminder. It would be more efficient if the user would be notified about the incoming overtime requests through email even without logging into the system. This will enable faster responses of the approvers to the team member's requests since the users are always monitoring their emails while on shift.

7.2 Forgot Password

In the current system, the users need to contact the administrator to reset their password and/or unlock their account in the event that they forgot their password. The proponent would like to improve this process by adding the forgot password feature to the system. With this feature, the users would be able to retrieve his or her password without the involvement of the administrator anymore. However, this may only be made possible once the proponent was given rights to Telus' internal mail server.

7.3 Mobile responsive pages

There are some elements in the pages of the system, such as the tables and forms, which get distorted in mobile view. The proponent would like to address this by making the pages more mobile responsive and compatible. However, this might entail more research and tests. Once this is achieved, users may be able to access the system through their mobile devices without having to open their work laptops.

7.4. Data Analytics

The proponent would like to improve the reports feature of the system by integrating a data analytics API. By adding this, the overtime data would be translated into visual reports and dashboards which the senior leaders in the manager's meeting would appreciate. This will enable users to better understand the reports, help them easily uncover trends, and derive valuable insights from it.

7.5 Unified Calendar

While the different calendars for leave projections and offset usage tracker already exist and are working as expected, it would be a nice-to-have enhancement to merge these calendars into one. This idea was also suggested by one of the participants during the System Usability Testing,

REFERENCES

- [1] "Add Advanced interaction controls to your HTML tables the free & easy way". *Data Tables*. [Online]. Available: <https://www.datatables.net/>. [Accessed: November 2022]
- [2] "Data Modeling: Conceptual vs Logical vs Physical Data Model". *Visual Paradigm Online*. [Online]. Available: <https://online.visual-paradigm.com/knowledge/visual-modeling/conceptual-vs-logical-vs-physical-data-model>. [Accessed: November 2022].
- [3] "Feature-rich And Draggable Event Calendar Plugin - FullCalendar". *jQuery Script.net*. [Online]. Available: <https://www.jqueryscript.net/time-clock/Full-Size-Drag-Drop-Calendar-Plugin-FullCalendar.html>. [Accessed: October 2022].
- [4] Rabelo, Juliano, "Three-Tier Architecture". *Technopedia*, January, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.techopedia.com/definition/24649/three-tier-architecture>. [Accessed December 12, 2022].
- [5] Sauro, Jeff PhD, "5 Ways to Interpret a SUS Score". *Measuring U*. September 18, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://measuringu.com/interpret-sus-score/>. [Accessed: December 9, 2022].
- [6] *Start Bootstrap*. [Online]. Available: <https://startbootstrap.com/>. [Accessed: June 2022].
- [7] Thornton, Jon, "jquery-timepicker". [Online]. Available: <https://www.jonthornton.com/jquery-timepicker/>. [Accessed: October 2022].
- [8] "What is Regression Testing? Definition, Tools, Method, And Example". *Software Testing Help*, December 5, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.softwaretestinghelp.com/regression-testing-tools-and-methods/>. [Accessed: December 28, 2022].
- [9] "Web APIs- Introduction". *W3schools*. [Online]. Available: https://www.w3schools.com/js/js_api_intro.asp. [Accessed: November 2022].

APPENDIX A:

PARTICIPATION AND DISCLOSURE AGREEMENT

Participation and Disclosure Agreement

My name is **Ma. Rossiya Anne Asinas**, a graduate student from University of the Philippines Open University (UPOU). I am inviting you to participate in the usability testing of my project called the **Overtime Management System**. This system aims to organize the overtime filing and scheduling of the UNIX Manila team under Telus International Digital Solutions (TIDS).

Given your experience and familiarity of the system, I believe your participation will bring valuable inputs to help me improve the project.

In this evaluation, you will fill out a set of questionnaires and answer interview questions. You will give me permission to use these responses as our data to measure the usability of my system. The results will be used for academic purposes only.

Your personal information will also be kept confidential within the UPOU Faculty of Information Communications Studies (FICS) only. It will not be used outside of this course.

If you have any questions about this project, please feel free to contact me at **mlasinas@up.edu.ph**.

Your participation in this survey is voluntary. You may choose not to participate and withdraw at any time. If you wish to participate, select "I agree" in the choices below:

APPENDIX B:

POST-TEST QUESTIONNAIRE SCORING SHEET

Participant #	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Q10
1	5	1	5	1	5	1	5	1	5	1
2	5	1	5	1	5	1	5	1	5	1
3	5	1	5	1	5	1	5	1	5	1
4	5	1	5	1	5	2	4	1	5	2
5	5	3	4	2	5	2	4	2	4	3
6	5	1	5	1	5	1	5	1	5	1
7	5	1	5	1	5	1	5	1	5	1
8	5	2	5	1	5	1	4	1	5	2
9	5	2	5	1	5	1	4	2	4	1
10	5	1	5	1	5	1	5	1	5	1

Table 6: Post Questionnaire Scoring Sheet of the Participants

APPENDIX C:

SOURCE CODE

The source code of the project can be found in the github link below:

https://github.com/mralasinas/ASINAS_IS295_OMS.git

NOTE: The github project is only accessible to collaborators.